

The problems in psychology.

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Annotation: this article describes the role of psychology in our lives, the existing laws on the works of psychologists and their usage application, existing drawbacks in the field, and changes and additions to the field.

A person lives in search of happiness, sometimes he understands it, sometimes he doesn't. In both cases, the goal is the same. Everyone chooses different ways to achieve the goal. What path to choose depends on the person. If a person is mentally mature, he will choose the right path and reach his destination. If mentally is poor, he will choose the wrong way and will not reach his destination. There is only one way to save a person from spiritual poverty: proper education from childhood. Are we ready to educate the young generation to be mature? What knowledge and skills do we need for this? In order to raise a child to be mentally mature, we must first of all raise the level of his physical health and mental education. Psychology is a science that combines physical and mental education. The lack of understanding of the science of psychology and the activities of psychologists in most parts of the population causes many problems in the society, in particular, crime, delinquency and other such complications related to young people.

The word psychology comes from two Greek words - "psyche" (soul) and "logos" (doctrine, word) and means "science of the soul" and firstly it is originated in the 17th century German philosopher Christian Vulf's work. It is such a powerful teaching that, it helps to solve many human problems easily. Wherever there are people, there is psychology. He is the sum of all our qualities. Its possibilities are very wide.

Building a family is the root of everything. A family watered with psychology does not die, just as a plant that drinks water from its roots does not wither. Orphans or children whose parents are still alive will not appear. Because many problems in the family arise from the fact that the parents do not pay enough attention and love to the child, and are not interested in their desire to talk with them. Children begin to look for the love and attention that is not found in the family on the street. As a result of early marriage, young people start a family without being ready for it, and their children and the whole society suffer.

It is no secret to any of us that there are many legal documents on the work of psychologists. Including: Cabinet of Ministers No. 472 dated 07.09.2019 "On further

improvement of our personnel training system in the field of psychology and measures to prevent violations in society" and Cabinet of Ministers dated 07.12.2019 "Students" We can give an example of many laws, such as on the further improvement of psychological and pedagogical support. If we get acquainted with the content of the laws, they set a number of tasks regarding the organization of training courses for psychologists, provision of methodological manuals, organization of service rooms of preventive inspectors in educational institutions, and equipment of service rooms. In order to ensure the implementation of laws, a number of funds have been spent from the state budget and, in some cases, from the private pockets of service representatives. The aim is to improve the quality of psychological services for the population. We developed laws and ensured their implementation, but we did not achieve the goal. Why? To find the answer to this question, just go to any educational institution and see from the surveillance camera records in the corridors how many times a week or a month the prevention inspectors visited the service rooms, how many students were brought to the service rooms by practicing psychologists and how long they interviewed them during the week rather than the day. It will be enough to review. due to the reduction in the number of working secretaries in many secondary schools, psychologists have become secretaries of principals or deputy principals for spiritual and educational affairs. Psychologists do not perform their duties in educational institutions. As a result, issues related to the mentality of students remain open. Students and our society as a whole still need psychological help. So what is the cause and solution of this urgent and big problem? The purpose of highlighting the above situations is not to blame the representatives of the industry. Isn't it time to change the requirements for them? The representatives of the field are working according to the requirements, that is, the high-ranking officials in the field accept the performance of tasks from the lower bodies only in reports, or the working groups that go to an institution to study are only interested in the material and technical base and equipment of the service rooms. Instead, the representatives of the field would have changed the work process if they were interested in real factors, i.e., talking to the students and how much the practical psychologists or prevention inspectors in the institution benefit them. After all, an offer is made according to demand everywhere.

As shown above, psychology has its place in every aspect of our life. However, we are not able to make good use of the field these days. Today, each of us needs a psychologist, but we don't understand it ourselves. There is a misconception among the population that only mentally ill people consult a psychologist. Because ordinary people have no understanding of the industry. This is where the real problem lies. It is necessary to create an understanding of the industry among the population. For this, it is enough for them to talk with psychologists once. You just need to give them a chance. That is, for example, every person has to deal with marriage registration authorities at least once during his life. That is, at the time when they get legally married, I think it is necessary for

young people to undergo an interview with a psychologist. In recent years, a "family center" has been established in each district. In the centers, young people who are on the verge of starting a family should come and be interviewed by persons working in various positions, such as a gynecologist, a lawyer, a psychologist, an imam-khatib, based on an invitation issued by the marriage registration authorities. But by now, not all of the persons mentioned in the invitation take the time to come to the family center. Because they witnessed in the first interviews that hearing their words is not interesting for young people in most cases. Unfortunately, today's youth have become restless. In addition, the officials do not receive a separate monthly salary for coming here, but this is an additional task assigned to them. I think that instead of all the officials mentioned in the invitation, it will be enough to organize only the position of a psychologist on the basis of marriage registration authorities. Only an experienced psychologist who is engaged in this task and receives a monthly salary for this can have a short conversation with young people and give them the necessary advice. And about psychology, the correct understanding of its possibilities is formed in young people. I think ordinary people will understand where the solution to the problems they face when they start family life is; only in this way it is possible to bring ordinary people into the psychological environment at a high level. This experience will soon show its results. It is necessary not to give a certificate of marriage to young people until the psychologist has signed and stamped the document with the content "I passed my interview". Here again, let's talk about supply and demand in the market economy. In order to get married, we impose a condition for young people to pass a medical examination, that is, we are interested in their physical maturity, but the problem of the level of spiritual maturity is still open.

In addition, persons who have filed for divorce must be sent to a psychologist's interview once. Then maybe the number of divorces would decrease.

The problem of the lack of professional personnel in the field passes before the eyes of a person who reads the above opinions. The reason for this is the lack of practice in university students. Students go officially practice but instead of applying the knowledge they have acquired in their field at the place of internship they become servants of the managers of the head of institution.

In conclusion, if we solve the problems related to psychology we will save the society from moral decline. The time has already comes for changes and additions to the field.